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New Tool for Calculating Land Surface Parameters

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Abstract— The computation of land surface parameters (LSPs) from digital elevation model (DEM) is one of the most common tasks in geomorphometry. While first- and second-order local LSPs, calculated from the first and second partial derivatives of elevation (such as slope, aspect, and curvatures), are widely applied, third-order LSPs (changes in curvature) remain underutilized due to computational challenges and limited tool support. To address this gap, we developed a tool capable of computing partial derivatives of elevation up to the third order and deriving a wide range of local LSPs. Using a 5×5 moving window and a least-squares-fitted approximation polynomial, the tool employs general mathematical matrix-based formulas rather than the modified direct calculation formulas for square grids commonly used in geomorphometry. This approach enables greater flexibility, supporting various polynomial degrees, non-square grid spacings, and incomplete moving window configurations at the edges of study areas. Despite its enhanced capabilities, the tool is computationally efficient and allows for the simultaneous calculation of all supported LSPs in a single run, significantly improving efficiency compared to existing tools. This innovation makes less common second-order LSPs, as well as third-order LSPs, more accessible and practical for broader applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the development of geomorphometry, the number of land surface parameters (LSPs) used to describe land surface properties has increased. While it is possible to create an unlimited number of LSPs, their utility for various analyses hinges on their interpretative potential. Local LSPs are functions of partial derivatives of elevation, and based on the highest required order of derivatives, they can be further classified into subgroups by order [1]. The most traditional and widely used LSPs are those of the first order (slope, aspect), while second-order LSPs (various curvatures) are also broadly applied. Third-order LSPs (changes in curvature) are less common but are crucial for their application in the delimitation of surface objects [2].

The computation of LSPs involves deriving partial derivatives to the required order and substituting them into the formula for a

specific parameter. These formulas are well-established and widely known, though there is significant confusion in their terminology and application, as demonstrated for second-order parameters in [3]. For gridded digital elevation models (DEMs) of land surfaces, various methods for deriving partial derivatives exist. For decades, methods for computing first- and second-order partial derivatives based on a moving 3×3 window have been in use. These methods are identified by the names of their developers, including Evans [4], Young [5], Zevenbergen and Thorne [6], and Shary [7]. The mentioned methods involve the use of various second-degree bivariate approximation polynomials. The calculations are simplified into forms directly suitable for computing first- and second-order partial derivatives based on a constant grid spacing in the x and y directions. These methods are also implemented in GIS tools.

For the computation of third-order partial derivatives, a polynomial of at least the third degree is required. To calculate 10 coefficients of total third degree bivariate polynomial, a 3×3 window is insufficient, necessitating the use of a 5×5 window. The principle is the same as for second-degree polynomials, though the calculations are somewhat more complex. Florinsky [8] introduced modifications and formulas for using a third-degree polynomial within a 5×5 window. This method has been implemented in computational tools (e.g., SAGA GIS, WhiteBoxTools), but only for the computation of first- and second-order partial derivatives. The limited support for third-order partial derivative calculations thus represents a restrictive factor that contributes to the limited adoption of third-order LSPs.

This led us to develop a tool capable of computing partial derivatives of elevation up to third order and using them to derive a wide range of LSPs. To derive the partial derivatives, a minimally required moving window of 5×5 is used. The tool employs an approximation polynomial fitted using the least squares method, similar to other approaches, such as the second-degree polynomial of Evans or the third-degree polynomial of Florinsky. However, the main difference is that it does not use modified formulas for

direct calculation of derivatives from the grid as is common in geomorphometry, but general mathematical matrix-based formulas, similar to [9]. This approach offers several advantages: straightforward application to polynomials of various degrees, support for grids with different spacing along the individual axes (essential for input in geographic coordinates), and the ability to handle incomplete 5×5 windows (at the edges of a study area), as further detailed below. With appropriate optimization, the computation is not significantly more demanding than analogous computations using the classical approach. Moreover, the purpose-built tool allows for the calculation of all supported LSPs in a single run, making it far more efficient than other existing tools.

II. METHODS

The main task in calculating LSPs involves computing the partial derivatives of elevation z (up to the required order for specific LSPs). This is based on the concept of the land surface being defined by a general bivariate function $z = f(x, y)$. A common approach involves fitting a bivariate polynomial, as presented above. To compute LSPs up to the third order, the minimum required polynomial degree is three. Shary [10] suggested that third-order LSPs for land surface description seems to be not feasible because of their excessive sensitivity to "noise". However, polynomial fitting using the least squares method mitigates data errors [2] (which [10] referred to as noise). Furthermore, advancements in DEM quality, driven by the LiDAR revolution, have seemingly reduced the prominence of data errors [11]. This improvement has opened the possibility of using higher-order polynomials, which may have a lesser impact on reducing data error. On the other hand, higher-order polynomials pose the risk of introducing artifacts, such as Runge's phenomenon. Therefore, for calculating third-order LSPs, polynomials of degree three or four are considered to be the most feasible options.

The total number of coefficients n in bivariate polynomials is calculated as

$$n = \frac{(d+1)(d+2)}{2} \quad (1)$$

where d is the degree of the polynomial. Thus, there are 10 and 15 coefficients for degrees 3 and 4, respectively. Using a 5×5 moving window provides sufficient data for the calculations, along with additional values for least squares fitting. This process creates an approximating surface with slight implicit smoothing.

In general, a bivariate polynomial $P(x, y)$ of total degree d , used for fitting to data points (x_i, y_i, z_i) , where z_i represents the elevation at (x_i, y_i) , is expressed as

$$P(x, y) = \sum_{j=0}^n c_j \cdot B_j(x, y) \quad (2)$$

where c represents the unknown coefficients to be determined, and B are the basis functions forming the basis function matrix A

$$A_{ij} = B_j(x_i, y_i) = x_i^{p_j} \cdot y_i^{q_j} \quad (3)$$

The members are the n combinations of exponents p, q such that $p + q \leq d$. A is a matrix of size $(num_points \times n)$. For example, for a third-degree polynomial and a full 5×5 moving window, A has a size of 25×10.

The solution for least squares fitting is obtained by solving the normal equations

$$M \cdot c = v \quad (4)$$

where M is the matrix

$$M = A^T \cdot A \quad (5)$$

and v is the right-hand side vector

$$v = A^T \cdot z \quad (6)$$

The coefficients c are computed as

$$c = M^{-1} \cdot v \quad (7)$$

The partial derivatives of a bivariate polynomial $P(x, y)$ are computed by differentiating each term of the polynomial individually. The partial derivative of the j -th basis function with respect to $x^p y^q$ is calculated as

$$\frac{\partial^{p+q} B_j}{\partial x^p \partial y^q} = \binom{p_j}{p} \cdot \binom{q_j}{q} \cdot x^{p_j-p} \cdot y^{q_j-q} \quad (8)$$

or derivative is zero, if $p > p_j$ or $q > q_j$. The contribution to the partial derivative of $P(x, y)$ is obtained by multiplying the derivative of the basis function by its corresponding coefficient c_j

$$\frac{\partial^{p+q} P}{\partial x^p \partial y^q} = \sum_{j=0}^n c_j \cdot \frac{\partial^{p+q} B_j}{\partial x^p \partial y^q} \quad (9)$$

Even though a fourth-order polynomial allows the calculation of fourth partial derivatives, only the first three orders are needed for LSP calculations, so $p + q \leq 3$ in (8) and (9).

III. RESULTS

A. Polynomial Fitting in a Grid

The described general method for polynomial least-squares fitting can approximate a surface based on any set of elevation points, provided the minimum required number of points for the selected polynomial degree (1) is met. However, when applied to a regular grid, as implemented in the presented tool, the uniform spacing allows for the use of relative x, y coordinates (with fixed step sizes dx, dy), enabling optimization of the calculations. This optimization involves precomputing the basis function matrix A and the M matrix. Consequently, calculations that would otherwise need to be repeated for each new point are accelerated by using these precomputed matrices.

With different values of dx and dy , it is straightforward to implement direct calculation of LSPs from geographic coordinates. For each grid row, the values of dx and dy in meters are computed using ellipsoidal calculations as recommend in [12]. This approach means that matrices A and M are not precomputed once per grid but rather once per grid row.

In special cases where not all input data are available in a 5×5 moving window, derivatives can still be calculated if there are enough points for the selected polynomial degree (Fig. 1 A). This provides an advantage over traditional approaches, which require a full moving window. The absence of a full moving window in some tools either prevents calculation (Fig. 1 D) or results in the addition of fictitious elevation values (e.g., duplicating the central pixel elevation), leading to inaccuracies (Fig. 1 B,C). In this case, only part of the optimization can be used: a subset of the relevant rows in the precomputed A matrix, based on the available grid nodes, is employed, while the M matrix must be recalculated.

Figure 1. Slope calculation [°] at the area edge (bordering no-data pixels): A – LSP Calculator (our tool), correct where sufficient data is available; B – WhiteBoxTools, unnaturally low edge slopes with visible artifacts; C – GRASS GIS (-e flag for edge computation), unnaturally low edge slopes; D – GRASS GIS, correct but with missing data at the edge.

B. Calculated Land Surface Parameters

Our tool calculates partial derivatives to compute a wide range of local LSPs up to the third order. From the set of first-order LSPs, slope gradient S and aspect A can be derived, along with variants such as $\sin S$, $\sin A$, and $\cos A$ for direct input into specific algorithms. A comprehensive set of curvatures (Fig. 2), representing second-order LSPs, can also be calculated. Unlike other software, which often provides only the most common curvatures, our tool is capable of calculating all the curvatures presented here. For third-order LSPs, which describe changes in curvatures, the tool supports the calculation of contour change of normal contour curvature ($k_n)_{cc}$, slope line change of normal contour curvature ($k_n)_{cs}$, and slope line change of normal slope line curvature ($k_n)_{ss}$. These curvature changes have been shown to be suitable for physically based land surface segmentation [13]. Examples of less common LSPs are shown in Fig. 3 and 4.

All supported LSPs can be computed in a single run of the tool. This approach is computationally efficient, as the calculated partial derivatives are reused in the LSP calculations. It is also user-friendly, allowing users to obtain a set of requested LSPs calculated at once. For clarity, all the equations for the calculated LSPs are provided in the documentation in the repository [14].

C. Algorithm Implementation

We implemented the described algorithms and developed the Land Surface Parameters Calculator, a command-line tool written in the Rust programming language. This tool is part of the broader Physical Geomorphometry Tools project, which focuses on physically based methods for analyzing landforms and land surface dynamics. Its goal is to provide useful tools for processing DEMs within this framework.

Figure 2. Set of land surface curvatures: schema, based on [3], later revised.

Figure 3. Casorati curvature [m^{-1}] computed by LSP Calculator (DEM section from Ponui Island, New Zealand).

Figure 4. Contour change of normal contour curvature ($(k_n)_{cc}$ [m^{-1}]) computed by LSP Calculator (DEM section from Ponui Island, New Zealand).

The command-line interface allows users to specify an input DEM file (in GeoTIFF format) and an output prefix for the results. Users can compute a full suite of LSPs or select specific parameters or groups of parameters based on their research needs. The output consists of parameter-specific GeoTIFF files, systematically named using the provided output prefix.

The tool supports parallel processing, utilizing multiple CPU cores for improved performance. It relies on GDAL for raster handling and requires a Rust development environment for building from source. The source code, along with detailed instructions for building and usage, is available on GitHub [14].

IV. CONCLUSION

The newly developed tool introduces the capability to compute LSPs from DEMs up to the third order, which were previously underutilized due to computational challenges and limited tool support. By enabling the calculation of a wide range of LSPs, it makes less common second-order and third-order LSPs more

accessible for broader applications, unlocking new possibilities for land surface analysis and geomorphological research. The tool is implemented in a modern programming language, incorporates various optimizations, and supports parallel processing for efficient calculations. Future efforts aim to improve its usability, provide a web service, and integration into advanced software.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Evans, I., and Minár, J., 2011. "A classification of geomorphometric variables", *Geomorphometry 2011* (Redlands, CA, USA, 7. – 11. 9. 2011). Eds. T. Hengl, I. S. Evans, J. P. Wilson, M. Gould, 105-107.
- [2] Minár, J., Jenčo, M., Evans, I.S., Minár, J., Kadlec, M., Krcho, J., Pacina, J., Burian, L., and Benová, A., 2013. "Third-order geomorphometric variables (derivatives): Definition, computation and utilization of changes of curvatures", *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 27(7), 1381–1402. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2013.792113>
- [3] Minár, J., Evans, I.S., and Jenčo, M., 2020. "A comprehensive system of definitions of land surface (topographic) curvatures, with implications for their application in geoscience modelling and prediction", *Earth-Science Reviews*, 211, 103414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2020.103414>
- [4] Evans, I.S., 1972. "General geomorphometry: Derivatives of altitude, and the descriptive statistics". In: Chorley, R. (ed.), *Spatial Analysis in Geomorphology*, London: Methuen & Co. Ltd, 17–90.
- [5] Young, A., 1972. "Slopes." Oliver & Boyd, Edinburgh. 288 pp.
- [6] Zevenbergen, L.W. and Thorne, C.R., 1987. "Quantitative analysis of land surface topography", *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 12:47–56.
- [7] Shary, P.A., 1995. "Land surface in gravity points classification by a complete system of curvatures", *Mathematical Geology* 27(3): 373–390.
- [8] Florinsky, I.V., 2009. "Computation of the third-order partial derivatives and derivation function from a digital elevation model", *International Journal of Geographical Information Science* 23 (2): 213–231.
- [9] Pacina, J., 2010. "Comparison of approximation methods for partial derivatives of surfaces on regular grids", *Geomorphologia Slovaca et Bohemica*, Volume I, 25–32.
- [10] Shary, P.A., Sharaya, L.S., and Mitusov, A.V., 2002. "Fundamental quantitative methods of land surface analysis." *Geoderma* 107 (1), 1-32.
- [11] Evans, I. S., Minár, J., Feciskanin, R., in review. Models of the land surface; Conceptual, Mathematical & Digital. In: Reuter, H.I., Grohmann, C.H., and Lecours, V. (eds.), *Geomorphometry: Concepts | Software | Applications*, 2nd ed.
- [12] Guth, P., and Kane, M., 2021. "Slope, aspect, and hillshade algorithms for non-square digital elevation models", *Transactions in GIS*, 25(5), 2309–2332. <https://doi.org/10.1111/TGIS.12852>
- [13] Minár, J., Dráguť, L., Evans, I. S., Feciskanin, R., Gally, M., Jenčo, M., and Popov, A., 2024. "Physical geomorphometry for elementary land surface segmentation and digital geomorphological mapping", *Earth-Science Reviews*, 248, 104631. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EARSCIREV.2023.104631>.
- [14] Feciskanin, R., Hajdúchová, V., 2024. "Land Surface Parameters Calculator", Available online: <https://github.com/xiceph/physical-geomorphometry-tools/tree/main/lsp-calculator>